

INTEGRATION OF A LEARNING LAUNCHPAD ON FLIP FOR SPEECH DELIVERY OF THE SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY, ENGINEERING, AND MATHEMATICS (STEM) STUDENTS

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Integration of a Learning Launchpad on Flip for Speech Delivery of the Science, Technology, Engineering, And Mathematics (STEM) Students

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the speech delivery level of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) students before and after the integration of a learning launchpad on Flip in terms of the principles of speech delivery such as articulation, modulation, stage presence, facial expressions, gestures, and movements and rapport with the audience. The chosen subjects of this study were the 36 officially enrolled STEM students in the first semester of the academic year 2023-2024 in a particular section in one of the private institutions in Bacolod City, Negros Occidental. A validated and reliability-tested research instrument used in this study was a researcher-made rubric that contained five items namely: articulation, modulation, stage presence, facial expressions, gestures, and movements and rapport with the audience. This study utilized an Experimental Research Design, specifically Quasi-experimental, since it aimed to evaluate intervention that does not use randomization. The results of the study showed that the speech delivery level of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) students in terms of the mentioned speech delivery principles before and after the integration of a learning launchpad on Flip was all very good. There was a significant difference in the stage presence and rapport with the audience of students while there was no significant difference found in articulation, modulation and facial expressions, gestures and movements as principles of speech delivery. Therefore, an enrichment program was made based on the results of the study.

Keywords: *learning, integration, launchpad, speech delivery*

Introduction

Mendenilla (2018) mentioned that Oral Communication subject should provide opportunity for students to practice authentic speaking by exposing them to target language using authentic input accessible online. Thus, the use of a learning launchpad on Flip would be one of the approaches. Serembus and Murphy (2020) defined Flip, formerly known as FlipGrid, as an online application that supports asynchronous learning through video-based activities that allows students to interact and engage with each other like a social community.

Gleason and Leandro (2022) stated that training to enhance the effectiveness of oral presentations is often neglected in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) fields. Murphy & Kelp (2023) mentioned that STEM students should be provided with trainings in science communication skills, especially inclusive science communication skills that would facilitate equitable community engagement and should be included in undergraduate STEM curricula that will facilitate an increase in their community engagement attitudes and behaviors.

The concerned academic institution in this study helps students become 21st century global leaders and professionals through tech-savvy programs and nurturing environment and processes. The institutional outcome states that it aims to produce leaders and professionals with critical thinking and decision-making skills, communication skills and lifelong learning competencies that are competitive both nationally and internationally. In relation to this, the core values of this institution are focused on integrity and excellence. Therefore, the students shall have to be 21st century global leaders and professionals with integrity and excellence in their chosen field (Riverside College, 2024).

The major concern of the researcher is the communicative competence of the students in Oral Communication in Context and to achieve it, mastering the students' speech delivery is a must since it has principles such as articulation, modulation, stage presence, facial expressions, gestures and movements, and rapport with the audience that they need to portray on Flip as a learning platform through a learning launchpad because as based from the admission records of the school, the grade 11 STEM students were able to utilize both modular (printed) and online learning (through a learning management system such as Google classroom) modalities which prompted the researcher to investigate their communication skills since they both came from different learning modalities. The researcher has also observed that these students were products of the pandemic that started in March of 2020 and that during the 1st quarter oral recitations of 2023, these students showed a struggle in articulating their answers in English which they will need to develop through a learning launchpad on Flip. Thus, this study was conducted to help develop the speaking skills of STEM students.

Research Questions

This study generally aimed to determine the effectiveness of integrating a learning launchpad on Flip for the speech delivery of STEM students enrolled in the first semester of academic year 2023-2024 in one of the higher education institutions in Bacolod City. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the speech delivery level of the STEM students before and after integrating a learning launchpad on Flip in terms of

the following delivery of speech principles:

- 1.1. articulation,
 - 1.2. modulation,
 - 1.3. stage presence,
 - 1.4. facial expressions, gestures and movements, and
 - 1.5. rapport with audience?
2. Is there a significant difference in the speech delivery level of STEM students before and after integrating a learning launchpad on Flip in terms of the aforementioned variables?
 3. What program may be developed based on the results of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

This study sought to discover the effectiveness of integrating a learning launchpad on Flip for the speech delivery of STEM students enrolled in the first semester of academic year 2023-2024 in one of the Senior High Schools in Bacolod City. This study utilized an Experimental Research Design, specifically Quasi-experimental, where subjects were assigned to groups based on non-random criteria (Thomas, 2024).

This research design was found appropriate by the researcher because this study involves an assessment before and after integrating a learning launchpad on Flip to the same set of subjects to determine their level of speech delivery.

Furthermore, not all sections of the STEM students in their Oral Communication subject were able to integrate a learning launchpad on Flip as a tool to support their learning. It was best to employ a single group pretest-posttest design that referred to a type of quasi experimental design in which the same dependent variable was to be measured using one group of participants only before and after intervention (Glen, 2022).

Respondents

Purposive sampling was used as it is suited to the researcher's convenience to monitor the group of students that underwent integration of a learning launchpad on Flip in a span of six weeks of the 2nd quarter of the first semester of academic year 2023-2024.

The inclusion criteria were added and discussed below in appropriately selecting the target subjects:

They should have experienced either modular (printed) and online (Google Classroom) learning modalities. As based on the institution's admission records of the school, 24 of them had modular (printed) learning modality and 12 of them had online (Google Classroom) learning modality.

They should have an active engagement on Microsoft Teams such as always on-time turning in of assignments etc. as shown in their Insight's activity.

They should be officially enrolled in Oral Communication in Context during the 1st semester of academic year 2023-2024.

They should have a complete attendance during the one month and a half implementation of their intervention.

Instrument

A researcher-made Pre-Assessment and Post-Assessment Rubric was used in this study that was rated by three experts before and after the integration of a learning launchpad on Flip which underwent a validity and reliability test that included 5 items.

The validated rubric through Good and Scates tool was about the principles of speech of delivery namely: Articulation, Modulation, Stage Presence, Facial Expressions, Gestures and Movements, and Rapport with the Audience that achieved an average of 4.6 that interpreted as highly valid.

The reliability test through Fleiss Kappa tool was administered to 15 students of STEM strand from a different section who had an Oral Communication in Context Subject that performed a 2-stanza of their written speech and was rated by three experts using this validated rubric which resulted to 11 out of 15 match and garnered an inter-rater reliability result of 0.716 which interpreted to a good level of agreement.

The instrument had a 5-point rating scale with mean range interpreted as follows: 0.00 - 5.20 - Poor; 5.21 - 11.4 - Fair; 11.4 - 17.6 - Good; 17.6 - 23.8 - Very Good; 23.8 - 30.0 - Excellent.

The learning launchpad on Flip was validated through Good and Scates tool by three master degree holders or higher related to the field before it was implemented to the subjects that lasted for six weeks.

For validity test, a 5-point rating scale was used and interpreted as: 1.00-1.79 (Strongly not valid), 1.80 - 2.59 (Not valid), 2.60 - 3.39 (Undecided), 3.40 - 4.19 (Valid), 4.20 - 5.00 (Highly valid).

For reliability test, this scaling was utilized for the interpretation: <0.00 (Poor agreement), 0.00 - 0.20 (Slight agreement), 0.21 - 0.40 (Fair agreement), 0.41 - 0.60 (Moderate agreement), 0.61 - 0.80 (Substantial agreement), 0.81 - 1.00 (Almost Perfect).

Once the validity was accomplished and reliability test was done and passed, a pretest was given to the subjects.

Procedure

The data gathering procedure was divided into pre-implementation stage, implementation stage, and post-implementation stage to better understand the flow of the study.

Pre-Implementation Stage

The researcher wrote a letter asking permission to conduct the study addressed to the principal of the concerned institution. She then signed the letter and endorsed the researcher to the office of the research department.

The researcher then prepared the letters for the validity and reliability test of the rubric to be sent to the experts and accomplished the forms for the conduct of the study to the research department of the chosen institution.

The researcher had the rubric validated by the three experts in English. The reliability testing was done by choosing 15 students from different sections to undergo the pre-assessment. They were rated by three experts using the validated rubric and they performed their written speech in 1-2 minutes only. After which, the raw data were forwarded to the statistician for the results using Fleiss Kappa.

Once the rubric had been successfully validated and underwent a reliability test, the researcher then prepared the learning launchpad on Flip and had it validated as well by three experts who have a master's degree in English and higher.

After which, the researcher then proceeded to the research department of the private institution and accomplished the forms for data gathering attaching the approved letter of permission by the principal. When both parties approved and signed, the researcher then let the subjects had the consent form signed for both pre-assessment and post-assessment.

Implementation Stage

The researcher conducted the pre-assessment a week before the integration of a learning launchpad started on Flip. The researcher invited three experts in English to rate the students' speech delivery using the rubric. Their performance was documented by the researcher for attendance of the respondents. The inter-raters were given option by the researcher to rate the respondents either on the MS Forms link or the hard copy given. However, they opted to use the hard copy of the validated rubric to rate the performance of the respondents. After the pre-assessment, the researcher asked the students to download the Flip application on their available devices. The selected respondents were briefed on the outline of activities using Flip in a span of six weeks.

The integration of a learning launchpad on Flip started the week after the pre-assessment was given. The selected respondents were the 36 respondents who had participated in the pre-assessment. They were able to comply to the integration of a learning launchpad on Flip in a span of six (6) weeks in their Oral Communication in Context class where feedback was given every week to improve their speech delivery.

Post-Implementation Stage

On the sixth week of integration, they were able to get the post-assessment which concluded their participation in the study. Their post-assessment scores served as their 2nd quarter major performance task. They were rated again for the post-assessment by the same set of inter-raters on the pre-assessment. The data were analyzed by the researcher with the help of the statistician. To consider the ethical standards, their contributions were held confidential.

Data Analysis

The data were analyzed and treated using the following statistical tools:

For statement of the problem number 1 which was to determine the speech delivery level of STEM students before and after integrating a learning launchpad on Flip, mean and standard deviation as statistical tools were used.

For statement of the problem number 2 which was to determine the significant difference in the speech delivery level of the STEM students before and after integrating a learning launchpad on Flip based on the following principles: articulation, modulation, stage presence, facial expressions, gestures and movements, and rapport with the audience, a t-test for related samples was used since the data were normally distributed.

A 5-point rating scale with the following mean ranges was used for the interpretation of the results: Poor (0.00 - 5.20), Fair (5.21 - 11.4), Good (11.4 - 17.6), Very Good (17.6 - 23.8) and Excellent (23.8 - 30.0).

Ethical Considerations

As defined by Bhandari (2021), ethical considerations in research were a set of principles that guide the research design process and

practices. There were principles that needed to be upheld and considered by the researcher and the respondents before, during and after conducting the study.

Before the study was conducted, the researcher secured an informed consent form that signified the respondents' willingness to participate in the study. They were also informed that the study was voluntary, and they could withdraw their participation anytime. Their vulnerability was also considered.

Their social value that refers to the relevance of the study to an existing social or health problem such that the results are expected to bring about a better understanding of related issues, or contribute to the promotion of well-being of individuals, their families, and communities had been cleared to the subjects of the study which was about their speech delivery skills.

To protect the respondents' anonymity, the respondents' rubric had no names collected from the respondents. The researcher applied the importance of data protection during the data collection and analysis phase to ensure the safekeeping of electronic and hardcopy connected to the study.

To inform them of the risks, benefits, and safety, a precaution was taken to minimize the negative impact of the study on the research participant's wellbeing.

To ensure justice, which requires the equitable distribution of both the burdens and the benefits of participation in research, a fair selection in the choice of subjects was considered.

To comply with transparency as one of the ethical guidelines, the ratings of the inter-rater, which were the physical sources of research data, were removed permanently from the Microsoft OneDrive with no way of retrieving them after the results of the study been disseminated through research presentation and publication.

Results and Discussion

This section focuses on the structured presentation of collected quantitative data for clear understanding. It uses statistical methods to identify and analyze patterns and trends within the data. The interpretation of these findings emphasizes their significance and implications, thereby enhancing our current understanding and offering valuable insights.

Level of Speech Delivery of the STEM Students Before and After Integrating a Learning Launchpad on Flip

The primary aim of this study was to evaluate the impact of incorporating a learning Launchpad on Flip on the speech delivery skills of STEM students. Specifically, it assessed changes in articulation, modulation, stage presence, facial expressions, gestures and movements, and audience rapport. Statistical methods, including the calculation of mean and standard deviation, were employed to analyze performance metrics before and after the intervention. The results are presented in Table 1.

The level of speech delivery of the STEM students before and after integrating a learning launchpad on Flip is very good in terms of articulation, modulation, stage presence, facial expressions, gestures and movements, and rapport with the audience with means ranging from 21.5 to 23.5.

The result of the learning launchpad integration on Flip for the STEM students suggested that their speech delivery level before is very good and still the same after the integration of a learning launchpad on Flip as based on the score's interpretation, in terms of articulation, modulation, stage presence, facial expressions, gestures, and movements and rapport with the audience as principles of speech delivery with little improvement.

Table 1. *Level of Speech Delivery of the STEM Students Before and After Integrating a Learning Launchpad on Flip*

Speech Delivery	Before			After		
	M	VI	SD	M	VI	SD
Articulation	23.1	VG	2.6	23.5	VG	2.4
Modulation	22.4	VG	2.5	22.7	VG	3.0
Stage Presence	21.5	VG	2.9	22.6	VG	2.8
Facial Expressions, Gestures, and Movements	22.7	VG	2.4	23.1	VG	2.4
Rapport with Audiences	21.5	VG	2.8	23.4	VG	2.3
Overall	22.2	VG	2.5	23.1	VG	2.5

Note: Poor (P) 0.00-5.20, Fair (F) 5.21-11.4, Good (G) 11.4-17.6, Very Good (VG) 17.6-23.8, Excellent (E) 23.8-30.0

The result also indicated that intervention needs improvement in order for them to be excellent as stipulated in the institutional outcomes and core values of their affiliated institution.

The result supported the study Salcedo and Rico (2022) where they stated that students struggled with enunciation, verbal fillers, and pronunciation when it comes to Articulation. In the study of Ramos and Thorkelson (2022), their results supported this study as well when they emphasized the importance of proper voice tone and behavior when delivering a speech in terms of Modulation. Furthermore, in terms of stage presence, facial expressions, gestures and movements, and rapport with the audience. Papanas et. al (2011) highlighted

that in order for a performance of the speaker to be successful, the speaker should make the most of their appearance, voice, eye contact and movement to achieve eloquence. Thus, as based on the related studies claims, the same result was revealed before and after the integration of a learning launchpad on Flip. This implies that the researcher may draft an enrichment program to improve the mentioned principles of speech delivery.

Difference in the Level of Speech Delivery of STEM Students Before and After Integrating the Learning Launchpad on Flip

The second major objective of this study is to assess the differences in speech delivery skills of STEM students before and after the integration of the Learning Launchpad on Flip. The results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. *T-test results for the Difference in the Speech Delivery Level of STEM Students Before and After Integrating the Learning Launchpad on Flip*

<i>Principles of Speech Delivery</i>	<i>Tests</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>t-ratio</i>	<i>p</i>
Articulation	Pre-Test	23.1	2.59	35	-0.91	.368
	Post-Test	23.5	2.37			
Modulation	Pre-Test	22.4	2.53	35	-0.73	.471
	Post-Test	22.7	2.98			
Stage Presence	Pre-Test	21.5	2.94	35	-2.26*	.030
	Post-Test	22.6	2.77			
Facial, Gestures and Movements	Pre-Test	22.7	2.41	35	-1.01	.319
	Post-Test	23.1	2.39			
Rapport with the Audience	Pre-Test	21.5	2.77	35	-4.05**	.000
	Post-Test	23.4	2.34			

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

Table 2 shows that there are significant differences in the speech delivery level of the STEM students during the pretest and posttest in terms of Stage Presence ($t(35) = -2.26$, $p = .030$) and Rapport with the Audience ($t(35) = -4.05$, $p < .001$) of the STEM students. While there are no significant differences in terms of Articulation ($t(35) = -0.91$, $p = .368$), Modulation ($t(35) = -0.73$, $p = .471$), and Facial Expressions, Gestures, and Movements ($t(35) = -1.01$, $p = .319$).

This implies that the posttest results are better than the pretest results which means that the learning launchpad on Flip intervention helped on the improvement of their stage presence and rapport with the audience as principles of speech delivery. While the STEM students have the same speech delivery level before and after the integration of a learning launchpad on Flip in terms of Articulation, Modulation, and Facial Expressions, Gestures, and Movements as principles of speech delivery.

The higher mean results in the post assessment were in line with McCabe's (2012) recommendations about the utilization of pedagogic approaches like task-based strategies that can enhance students' oral communication skills which was first affirmed by Alejo (2010) which highlighted how task-based strategies significantly improved students' communicative competence. Furthermore, Moron and Velasco (2023) revealed that an exposure to the teaching activities for speaking, story completion and picture description had made a significant difference to the articulation and other speech delivery principles of the students. Thus, the higher means that the respondents achieved after the post- assessment were positively relevant for stage presence and rapport with the audience.

For articulation, modulation, facial expressions, gestures and movements with no significant differences, a hypothesis could be made that these principles take time to develop and the learning launchpad intervention may not be sufficient to make significant changes.

Fuchs et. al (2021) stated that interventions ranged from roughly 6 weeks to 6–7 months in duration. In this study, a six-week duration was followed after the pre-assessment of the STEM students. However, Marek (2019) argued that research touting positive results resulting from short-duration use must be interpreted as tentative at best. Only studies in which the intervention or learning activity lasts for eight weeks or more should be considered to be generalizable. With this, the researcher had to create an enrichment program about the learning launchpad on Flip that will follow a longer intervention duration.

In terms of stage presence, this result is supported by the article of Den Bergh (2023) which stated that stage presence can be developed and cultivated. Furthermore, this was backed by the study of Papanas et.al (2011) that in stage presence, speakers must appear calm and confident and their clothes should be well-chosen without drawing too much attention on themselves. In this study, the students wore comfortable casual attire in delivering their performance which was appropriate for the occasion and may have contributed to the overall stage presence of the STEM students.

In the study of Raja (2017), it was stated that speakers should seek feedback of the audience during practice sessions or can ask someone to record the talk because watching it several times for self-criticism also helps facilitate the learning and improvement process. This

had been true in the learning launchpad on Flip since the feedback was given online and students were able to view their own recording and their classmates' as well so they were able to learn from each other especially in the aspect of stage of presence.

It was also revealed in the study of Raja (2017) that exposure to virtual environment can facilitate student confidence and enable them to face audience irrespective of the size which in this study, Flip has greatly provided and contributed to the stage presence of the STEM students.

Kilag et.al (2023) had recommended that public speakers must maintain a good posture and respect the audience while maintaining eye contact with all members attending the event of which was at utmost importance especially in stage presence as a principle of speech delivery.

In terms of rapport with the audience, this result was in line with the study of Adams (2022) which concluded that the implementation of body language and the use of a strong and confident voice can help an audience focus on the delivery of a speech. This was relevant in this study because they were able to connect with their audience. This statement was supported by Courtney and Smallwood (2020) where they stated that making eye contact, smiling, and using gestures can help establish a connection with the audience and make them feel more engaged with the speaker's speech.

This was also supported by the study of Clarion et.al (2022) where based on their results, they have recommended that English language teachers should expedite actions to improve the techniques used in speech delivery and audience analysis. Also, they mentioned that the school authorities should supply speech delivery tools (computers, etc) to enhance the performance of students in speech delivery and audience analysis.

In terms of Articulation as a speech delivery principle that saw a minor increase in its mean score but not statistically significant, this implies that there is a need for the articulation of the grade 11 students to be improved.

This was supported by the study of Ong, Charito (2023) where proficiency in speech articulation was intricately interwoven with the development of macro skills, especially in the domains of comprehension and communication and that the ability to articulate sounds accurately influenced their oral expression, comprehension of spoken language, and overall communication effectiveness. To do this, integrating speech articulation exercises into curricula could enhance students' overall language comprehension, boosting their ability to interpret and respond to complex ideas in various academic disciplines. However, for the integration to be effective, articulation was an aspect of language that required intricate motor execution that needed to be highlighted and that elaborative system of speech production required the use of higher order executive function (EF) skills such as cognitive abilities including, but not limited to, planning and goal setting, inhibition, working memory, attention, emotional control, shifting, and problem solving and that speech production may also serve as predictor for executive function because there was an evidence for the interrelatedness between many domains of executive functions and an integral component of language: speech sound production (Netelenbos et al, 2018). Therefore, there should be a series of speech activities as refreshers that STEM students should undergo which are focused on the executive functions.

In terms of Modulation that also achieved a minor increase in its mean score but not statistically significant, this implies that a little to no improvement was made in modulation as a speech delivery principle before and after the integration of a learning launchpad of the grade 11 students.

As stated in the study of Wang et.al (2020), there was a challenge to master different voice modulation skills even though there are many available guidelines, they were often not practical enough to be applied in different public speaking situations, especially for novice speakers. This meant that students must be introduced to a lot of voicing practices where they could master different modulation skills. Also, they have mentioned in their study the importance of immediate and quantitative visual feedback to be provided for students' guidance for further improvement.

In the study of Leongómez et.al (2021), dynamic voice production and perception formed a regular part of everyday communication, whether physically 'voice-to-voice' or online and virtual. Thus, this should be studied more. This was supported by the study of Pisanski et. al (2018), where they have stated that voice modulation technology could be beneficial in improving vocal confidence and fluency with 95.8% of users expressing satisfaction with the results.

In terms of facial expressions, gestures, and movements, improvement was also seen through an increase mean after the integration of a learning launchpad on Flip but was found still to be not statistically significant.

This result is in line with the recent study of Kilag et. al (2023) which concluded that the speakers should keep their hands and arm moving at all times while occasionally returning their hands to their waistline area and use various facial gestures and expressions to help entice the audience. This might not be performed well by the students before and after the integration of a learning launchpad on Flip.

In the study of Rodero et. al (2022), it was revealed that happiness was the most pleasant and positive expression, followed by confidence, indifference, shyness, and anger, when the participants watched the speakers before the presentation. The speakers' expressions were perceived as more intense before the speech than during the discourse.

Their study implied that there was a need for speaker's happiness to be seen before the presentation to better gauge the message of the speech and happiness can be shown through smiling. Therefore, students should study their speech so that they will show the right facial expressions, gestures and movements.

Conclusions

Based on the formulated findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

There is a need for more practice activities for the STEM students to do on the learning launchpad on Flip concerning the five speech delivery principles: articulation, modulation, stage presence, facial expressions, gestures and movements and rapport with the audience for them to acquire the excellent level of speech delivery.

Given that there is more improvement in stage presence and rapport with the audience, a longer intervention duration is needed to be implemented for articulation, modulation, and facial expressions, gestures and movements as principles of speech delivery in the learning launchpad on Flip enrichment program.

Based on the foregoing findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are hereby proposed:

English Language Teachers. The results of the study may serve as their basis in teaching the principles of speech delivery: Articulation, Modulation, Stage Presence, Facial Expressions, Gestures and Movements, and Rapport with the audience as one of the competencies to be mastered in learning Oral Communication in Context especially to their STEM students. They may also undergo relevant trainings that may be used for the implementation of the enrichment program especially in speech delivery.

School Administrators. They may consider allocating budget for the implementation of English language programs particularly in speech delivery of the English teachers for the improvement of the speaking skills of the students that could benefit the whole institution that is in congruence to its mission and vision. They can also benchmark on curriculum revamp of activities that will surely make graduates of 21st century global leaders and professionals with integrity and excellence.

School Educational Technology Officers. They may use their positions to find more language improvement technology applications in improving the English-speaking skills of the students. The results may also encourage them to find other technology applications that English teachers could utilize in their classroom instruction aside from Flip. They may also conduct trainings regarding new technology applications that English language teachers could make the most of in teaching and learning activities.

Parents. As learning partners, they may keep track of their child/ren's progress in their English-speaking skills by initiating conversations using technology application/s.

Students. They may explore more technology applications to help them develop their confidence in speaking. This may encourage them to prioritize honing their public speaking skills that they may find beneficial and college ready STEM students. They may actively participate in public speaking related contests that the school may provide for them.

Researcher. She may be able to craft a learning launchpad on Flip enrichment program that can be used as a remedial program for the academic year 2024-2025 specifically for articulation, modulation, and facial expressions, gestures and movements. This may also enable her as well to try the other macro-skills of the English language to be tested and conduct it on a larger sample in her next research endeavors.

Future Researchers. This study may serve as their basis for the improvement of the other macro-skills like reading, writing and listening through technology-aided interventions. This may also serve as their example to try this to other strands especially HUMSS (Humanities and Social Sciences) and ABM (Accountancy and Business Management).

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